

Sustainable Conservation and Restoration of Built Cultural Heritage: Introduction to the SCORE Project

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Résumé

Le projet « Sustainable COnservation and REstoration of built cultural heritage » (SCORE) vise à rassembler un groupe intersectoriel, international et multidisciplinaire qui comprend un large éventail d'acteurs - y compris des scientifiques de différentes disciplines, des sociétés de conseil, des organismes de formation et des organisations non gouvernementales. – afin de renforcer la recherche collaborative et l'innovation dans la conservation, la restauration et la réhabilitation respectueuses de l'environnement. Intégrer les exigences du patrimoine culturel dans les éléments économiques et sociaux du développement durable devient essentiel et nécessite une main-d'œuvre hautement qualifiée pour la conception, l'exécution et les travaux de conservation. L'objectif du projet SCORE est de réduire l'empreinte écologique des matériaux et méthodes employés dans la conservation du patrimoine culturel bâti.

Mots clés : patrimoine culturel bâti, restauration verte, changement climatique, économie circulaire

Keywords: built cultural heritage, green restoration, climate change, circular economy

Extensive research and innovation efforts have been made worldwide to conserve Built Cultural Heritage (BCH), but a lot more must be done to estimate the ecological footprint of the materials and methods employed during conservation works. Matching cultural heritage requirements with ecological, economic, and social aspects¹ becomes essential. We should combine the needs of society with the obligation to protect environmental and natural resources while contributing to sustainable future development: circular economy principles.

The SCORE project aims to bring together an intersectoral, international and multidisciplinary group that includes materials scientists, biology and civil engineering researchers, restorers, archaeologists, art historians, Life Cycle Assessment specialists, climatologists, practitioners, consulting companies, training organisations, decision-makers and non-governmental organisations in order to strengthen collaborative research and innovation in eco-friendly conservation, restoration, and rehabilitation. It aims to support the development of a series of innovative materials and methods dedicated to BCH conservation, integrating the circular economy concept, climate change and ecological footprint constraints.

Objectives and Actions

The SCORE project pursues three main actions of sustainable development:

- 1) Development of 'green' innovations: materials and methods for the conservation of ancient buildings based on a circular economy philosophy.
- 2) Two-way assessment of impacts of the environment on materials and of materials on the environment: climate conditions and atmosphere composition determine BCH materials' behaviour, and, at the same time, the BCH conservation impacts greenhouse gas emissions and then climate change.
- 3) Transfer to society: training and knowledge transfer on both innovative and traditional materials and methods with a low environmental impact.

The research and innovation action rely on two kinds of built cultural heritage in two geographical and climatic areas: vernacular built cultural heritage in Europe and archaeological sites in Yucatan (Mexico). Although different, these two kinds of built heritage use similar materials and construction techniques that can be transmitted and adapted from one to another. In both cases, BCH faces the same environmental constraints:

- Climate change, which threatens the protection of both monuments and vernacular buildings, in the light of current and future climate conditions^{2 3};
- The ecological footprint of the restoration (monuments) and rehabilitation (vernacular) materials and methods, which must be minimised.

The main climate types of the selected areas are extremely different, according to the Köppen-Geiger climate classification⁴: equatorial in Latin America (A) and several different warm temperate climates (C) in Europe. This allows us to study the behaviour and durability of BCH conservation materials and techniques in different climate conditions, generating different weathering processes such as biological colonisation in climate A, salt crystallisation in climate C, etc., to extend the results obtained to other world regions.

Built heritage conservation materials should meet three criteria: innocuity, compatibility and retractability^{5 6}. Even if restoration methods for monuments are subjected to more constraints than vernacular cultural heritage, sustainability aspects must not be neglected. Research on traditional building techniques and new inorganic materials will help to reduce the environmental impact of restoration campaigns. Practitioners and the environment are potentially exposed to risk factors during restoration works; a circular economy model must minimise those risks⁷.

Figure 1. SCORE case studies

The selection of case study (**Figure 1**) sites was based on several criteria: (i) historical and architectural interest, (ii) geographical proximity and accessibility by research groups, (iii) research groups' previous experience in the employment of material and building techniques, (iv) a wide range of climatic conditions. More details about the case studies can be found at www.score-project.net.

To achieve its objectives, the SCORE project implements a designed bespoke methodology which consists in working through 'implementation loops', as detailed below and in **Figure 2**.

- 1) Bibliographic review, documentary and 'in-situ' study of sites.
- 2) Laboratory and 'in-situ' studies to characterise ancient materials, their conservation degree, composition, and physical properties.
- 3) Design of new materials: mortars and renders, bricks, consolidators, water repellents, biocides, etc.
- 4) Durability tests in the laboratory and 'in-situ' to determine the long-term behaviour of ancient and new materials in different environmental conditions. According to the obtained results, formulations may be reviewed.

- 5) Environmental performance and eco-friendly characteristics of materials and conservation methods. Life Cycle Assessment methodology will be used. The results will be used to review the proposed formulations.
- 6) Durability test results will be used to establish new dose-response functions for different weathering effects under continuous climate changes or extreme events on BCH conservation.
- 7) Past climate data and simulations of climate models for future periods will allow us to predict future climate conditions and identify their differences from past ones.
- 8) Past, current, and future weathering material will be determined using dose-response functions and climate model 'predictions'. Formulations will be approved or redesigned based on the obtained results.
- 9) Validation of new materials and methods if they fulfil all the required conditions: compatible with real case materials, eco-friendly and durable in the present and future conditions.

Figure 2. SCORE working methodology.

The SCORE project's expected results are:

- 1) Green restoration and rehabilitation products and methods: new products and methods proposed to practitioners, project managers, public and private owners.
- 2) Research contributions: a) new dose-response functions to estimate the effect of continuous processes (temperature rise, relative humidity changes, mean rain, etc.), b) critical threshold for extreme events (heatwave, rainstorms, dry seasons, etc.), c) future weathering maps in selected areas based on climate model simulations.
- 3) Training and academic actions, and dissemination of results.
- 4) Development of a large international and multidisciplinary network dedicated to green restoration and rehabilitation projects.

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